

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/simpat

Analysis and optimizations of PMI and rank selection algorithms for 5G NR

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ns-3
5G-LENA
PMI and RI selection
CSI feedback
Codebook-based precoding type-I
System-level simulation
5G NR

ABSTRACT

Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) is crucial for enhancing spectral efficiency, channel capacity, coverage, and robustness. However, it requires significant computations to determine a precoding matrix for transmitted data streams. In closed-loop MIMO, as adopted in 3GPP 5G NR, these computations occur on the user side. To avoid transmitting large matrices, 3GPP defined codebooks with pre-defined precoding matrices indexed by the Precoding Matrix Indicator (PMI). The User Equipment (UE) selects a PMI and a Rank Indicator (RI) to report to the Next Generation Node Base (gNB) as part of the Channel State Information (CSI) feedback. PMI/RI selection can be done via exhaustive search or more efficient techniques, which are crucial for real UE implementations due to their impact on computational complexity and energy consumption. This paper analyzes various PMI/RI selection techniques using the open-source ns-3 5G-LENA simulator. We have implemented state-of-the-art techniques in the system-level simulator and carried out extensive simulation campaigns. Also, we propose new PMI/RI selection methods by focusing on performance versus computational complexity trade-offs. Our proposed techniques show a superior simulation speedup (3.71x to 1.119x) with minimal throughput degradation (3% to 3.3%) compared to exhaustive search, depending on sub-band downsampling settings. Other state-of-the-art techniques implemented exhibit greater throughput losses (up to 8.3%) for a lower speedup (up to 3.54x) or similar losses with smaller speedups and potential slowdowns.

1. Introduction

Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) technology is known in textbooks for several decades. It is used in 4G-LTE and 5G-NR, and has been in Wi-Fi products for more than 20 years. In a downlink 5G NR MIMO system, a base station (gNB in 5G NR) can send multiple data streams to the user (UE in 5G NR) simultaneously, for a given time/frequency resource. This results in a significant increase of the transmission data rate, which ideally scales with the number of MIMO streams. For optimal MIMO performance, the gNB should apply a precoding matrix (at the transmitter) that determines how the signal is aligned relative to the channel, and the UE (at the receiver) should apply a receive filter to suppress inter-stream interference and recover each stream. The precoding matrix that provides the maximum Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) for the given channel matrix is usually selected [1]. The receive filter is usually designed to reduce the mean square error between the transmitted and decoded data symbols. 3GPP adopted the Minimum Mean Squared Error Interference Rejection Combining (MMSE-IRC) receiver, as it provides a good balance between performance (mean square error reduction) and implementation complexity, as it is a linear receiver.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpat.2025.103162>

Received 17 February 2025; Received in revised form 27 May 2025; Accepted 27 May 2025

Available online 19 June 2025

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In 3GPP, a closed-loop MIMO mechanism is defined, in which the Channel State Information (CSI) is acquired at the gNB thanks to CSI feedback from the UE. CSI feedback includes the Precoding Matrix Indicator (PMI), the Rank Indicator (RI), and the Channel Quality Information (CQI) [2]. To reduce feedback complexity and overhead, 5G NR has adopted codebook-based precoding. Thus, the selection of the precoding matrix is done by the UE and reported in the PMI through an index of a set of predefined precoding matrix from a codebook. In addition, the UE also reports the RI as part of the CSI feedback, which indicates to the gNB how many streams to use for that UE. Finally, the CQI is mapped through a table to determine the Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) index used for transmission, which corresponds to a modulation order and effective code rate. 5G NR uses the same MCS for a given transport block that can encapsulate up to 4 streams per UE, and so the same MCS is used for the multiple streams.

5G NR supports two types of codebooks for MIMO: Type-I and Type-II [2]. Type-I codebook is mainly used for single-user MIMO and is based on the same logic as the LTE codebook, while the Type-II codebook is mostly for multi-user MIMO and adopts a more generic mathematical formula with many of the parameters. In the case of Type-I (single-panel), the precoding matrix is expressed as the product of two matrices, one including wideband and long-term precoding and another for the sub-band and frequency-dependent precoding.

In the case of codebook-based MIMO, the best PMI and RI can be determined by an exhaustive search over the codebook, to select the precoding matrix and the rank that maximizes the SINR, the channel capacity, or any other metric of interest. However, the size of the codebook scales with the number of antenna ports at the gNB. Also, 5G NR supports sub-band CSI reporting for PMI and CQI, and so the PMI reports (and computations) scale with the number of sub-bands in the system. Note that the sub-band size defined for CSI reporting (i.e., number of PRBs/sub-band), depends on the total number of PRBs in the system. As a matter of fact, 5G NR supports up to 256 antenna ports [3] and the number of sub-bands can go up to 18 (for example in the case of 72 PRBs in the band with a sub-band size of 4 PRBs/sub-band [2]). Therefore, an exhaustive search becomes prohibitive for a large number of antenna ports and/or sub-bands. In addition, note that PMI and RI search is performed at the UE side, thus significantly affecting UE computational overhead and energy consumption.

This is why low-complexity precoding selection algorithms, including codebook-based PMI/RI selection algorithms, have attracted a lot of attention in recent years [4–15]. Examples of such algorithms developed in partnership or by equipment manufacturers include search-free techniques proposed in [4] and in [12,15]. There are also techniques with heuristics to prune the search space [5,7,8,10,11,14], such as the RI estimation techniques proposed in [5,7]. Machine-learning based techniques were also proposed in [6,9,13]. One of the drawbacks of the evaluations of already available techniques in the literature is that they have been evaluated through custom link-level simulations and/or considering just low-layer metrics. Therefore, the implementation and comparison in a system-level network simulator is missing. Implementation of MIMO and associated PMI/RI searches in network simulators is essential to observe the trade-offs that high-fidelity PHY models have on the computational complexity of the full 5G NR system.

In this paper, we review available RI and PMI selection methods in the literature, and propose and implement new PMI/RI selection methods. For that, we adopt a general nomenclature, valid to compare all available methods. Notably, we focus on a system-level perspective, including all variables that may affect the RI/PMI selection in a full system-level simulation setup. Unlike other studies, our analysis and simulations consider all the sub-bands within a bandwidth part. Then, we implement and compare various techniques proposed in the literature against our proposed PMI/RI selection techniques through simulation campaigns using the ns-3 5G-LENA open-source network simulator [16]. The implemented techniques include: the exhaustive PMI/RI search, Sasaoka's technique [5], Maleki's technique [12], and an ideal PMI/RI technique (used for benchmarking purposes). Simulation results in ns-3 allow examining how network performance is influenced by PMI/RI selection and which is the computational complexity associated to each technique. The proposed methods have been released in open source in ns-3 5G-LENA [17].

In summary, the contributions of this paper are as follows:

- review and summarize available PMI/RI selection methods, through a general system model nomenclature that is valid for all of them,
- propose new PMI/RI selection methods, for the general system set-up, focused on reducing the search space and execution time,
- implement available and proposed PMI/RI selection methods in the ns-3 5G-LENA network simulator, extending some of the available PMI/RI methods to account for all the system variables (e.g., number of sub-bands) and considering real implementation constraints (e.g., HARQ retransmissions, delays in precoding and rank selection updates)
- analysis, evaluation, and comparison of all the PMI/RI methods using the end-to-end system-level ns-3 network simulator. Differently from previous works that just simulate the physical layer, ns-3 allows extracting key end-to-end performance indicators (such as throughput) and execution time by using a close-to-real implementation of 5G NR standard-compliant protocols and thus account for the effect and interplay of important mechanisms such as HARQ retransmissions, link adaptation, precoding/rank/MCS delay updates according to the actual reports, interference, and channel/propagation condition changes.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the system model. Section 3 reviews codebook Type I and how PMI and RI are reported in 5G NR specifications. Then, Section 4 summarizes available RI selection methods, and Section 5 highlights PMI selection methods and the associated algorithms. Next, Section 6 presents new proposals for RI and PMI selection, by considering computational complexity reduction as main objective. Section 7 includes the simulation results and performance analysis, by using ns-3 network simulator with the 5G-LENA NR module. Finally, Section 8 concludes the paper and highlights future research lines.

2. System model

Consider a MIMO 5G NR downlink system composed of M gNBs, each serving a single UE on a given frequency resource (PRB in 5G NR) and time resource (time slot in 5G NR). Therefore, we get an interfered single-user MIMO system in each PRB, with up to M gNBs transmitting each to 1 UE (and so up to M UEs in the system depending on the scheduling decisions). Assume each gNB is equipped with N_T transmit antenna ports, each UE has N_R receive antenna ports,¹ and there are K PRBs in the channel. Let $\mathbf{H}_{j,u,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_T}$ denote the channel matrix between the transmit antenna ports at the j th gNB and the receive antenna ports at the u th user in the k th PRB.² Let $\mathbf{W}_{u,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times v_u}$ denote the transmit precoding matrix that the u th gNB uses to transmit v_u (data) streams towards its intended u th user in the k th PRB. This way, the transmitted power by the u th gNB in the k th PRB can be expressed as: $p_{u,k} = \text{Tr}(\mathbf{W}_{u,k} \mathbf{W}_{u,k}^H)$, being $\text{Tr}(\cdot)$ the trace operator. To achieve multiple data stream transmission, the following constraints must be satisfied: $v_u \leq N_T$ and $v_u \leq N_R$, and so $v_u \leq \min(N_T, N_R)$.

Assuming narrowband transmissions for a given PRB, the equivalent baseband signal $\mathbf{y}_{u,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times 1}$ observed at the u th user in the k th PRB is:

$$\mathbf{y}_{u,k} = \mathbf{H}_{u,u,k} \mathbf{W}_{u,k} \mathbf{b}_{u,k} + \mathbf{n}_{u,k}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{b}_{u,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{v_u \times 1}$ contains the symbols transmitted by the u th gNB towards its serving (u th) user, and \mathbf{n}_u is the noise-plus-interference received at the u th user, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{n}_{u,k} = \sum_{j=1, j \neq u}^M \mathbf{H}_{j,u,k} \mathbf{W}_{j,k} \mathbf{b}_{j,k} + \mathbf{a}_{u,k}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_{u,k}$ refers to the additive noise vector with covariance matrix $\mathbf{A}_{u,k}$. Assuming that interference is treated as noise and that a linear receive filter is applied at the receiver (the UE) the symbols are estimated at the u th user in the k th PRB as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{b}}_{u,k} = \mathbf{R}_{u,k}^H \mathbf{y}_{u,k}, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{u,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times v_u}$ is the linear receive filter applied at the u th user.

The mean square error (MSE) for the symbols transmitted towards the u th user in the k th PRB can be expressed through the so-called MSE-matrix $\mathbf{E}_{u,k} = \mathbb{E}\{(\hat{\mathbf{b}}_{u,k} - \mathbf{b}_{u,k})(\hat{\mathbf{b}}_{u,k} - \mathbf{b}_{u,k})^H\} \in \mathbb{C}^{v_u \times v_u}$, being $\mathbb{E}\{\cdot\}$ the expectation operator. The receive filter that minimizes the MSE, i.e., $\text{Tr}(\mathbf{E}_{u,k})$, is the MMSE-IRC receiver [1].

The MMSE-IRC receiver is given by: $\mathbf{R}_{u,k}^{\text{mmse}} = (\mathbf{H}_{u,u,k} \mathbf{W}_{u,k} \mathbf{W}_{u,k}^H \mathbf{H}_{u,u,k}^H + \mathbf{C}_{u,k})^{-1} \mathbf{H}_{u,u,k} \mathbf{W}_{u,k}$,³ where $\mathbf{C}_{u,k}$ is the covariance of the noise-plus-interference received at the u th user in the k th PRB:

$$\mathbf{C}_{u,k} = \sum_{j=1, j \neq u}^M \mathbf{H}_{j,u,k} \mathbf{W}_{j,k} \mathbf{W}_{j,k}^H \mathbf{H}_{j,u,k}^H + \mathbf{A}_{u,k}. \quad (4)$$

Note that $\mathbf{C}_{u,k}$ admits a Cholesky ‘‘LLT’’ decomposition as follows: $\mathbf{C}_{u,k} = \mathbf{L}_{u,k} \mathbf{L}_{u,k}^H$. This allows transforming the received signal in Eq. (1) through the following equivalent representation: $\mathbf{y}_{u,k}^{\text{eq}} = \mathbf{L}_{u,k}^{-1} \mathbf{y}_{u,k} = \mathbf{L}_{u,k}^{-1} \mathbf{H}_{u,u,k} \mathbf{W}_{u,k} \mathbf{b}_{u,k} + \mathbf{L}_{u,k}^{-1} \mathbf{n}_{u,k}$, for which the second term ($\mathbf{L}_{u,k}^{-1} \mathbf{n}_{u,k}$) has an identity covariance matrix (also known as interference whitening process) [1].

Using the MMSE-IRC receiver, the MSE-matrix results [1]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}_{u,k} &= (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{W}_{u,k}^H \mathbf{H}_{u,u,k}^H \mathbf{C}_{u,k}^{-1} \mathbf{H}_{u,u,k} \mathbf{W}_{u,k})^{-1} \\ &= (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{W}_{u,k}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_{u,u,k}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_{u,u,k} \mathbf{W}_{u,k})^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_{x,x}^k = (\mathbf{L}_x^k)^{-1} \mathbf{H}_{x,x}^k$ represents the interference-normalized channel matrix. The channel matrix is obtained assuming ideal estimation upon reception of the Channel State Information-Reference Signal (CSI-RS).

This way, the SINR of the r_u th stream ($r_u = 1, \dots, v_u$) of the u th user in the k th PRB ($\gamma_{u,r,k}$) is expressed as [1]:

$$\gamma_{u,r,k} = 1/\mathbf{E}_{u,k}(r, r) - 1, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{E}_{u,k}(r, r)$ denotes the r th diagonal element of the MSE matrix $\mathbf{E}_{u,k}$ in Eq. (5). Let us note that thanks to the introduction of the interference normalized channel $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_{u,u,k}$, we only need $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_{u,u,k}$ and $\mathbf{W}_{u,k}$ to represent the signal for the u th user in the k th PRB and extract the SINRs for its streams.

Similarly, the channel capacity of the u th user in the k th PRB is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{u,k} &= -\log_2 \det(\mathbf{E}_{u,k}) \\ &= \log_2 \det(\mathbf{I} + \bar{\mathbf{H}}_{u,u,k} \mathbf{W}_{u,k} \mathbf{W}_{u,k}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_{u,u,k}^H). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

¹ To simplify the presentation, we assume the same number of transmit and receive antenna ports at gNBs and UEs, respectively, but the system model could be easily extended to support asymmetric configurations.

² Note that $\mathbf{H}_{j,u,k}$ is the equivalent channel between transmit and receive antenna ports and so, with this formulation, it encapsulates the wireless propagation channel between all the transmit and receive antenna elements as well as the transmit and receive analog beamforming. Our problem formulation is general for any spatial channel model, either coming from a stochastic channel modeling (e.g., the 3GPP spatial channel model developed in [18]) or a deterministic channel model (e.g., Ray Tracing-based channel models).

³ Note that the MMSE-IRC receiver needs to perform a matrix inversion, which can be a difficult operation in practical environments. Therefore, adaptive estimations using recursive formulations could be used, but are left as future work.

3. 5G NR Precoding Type-I

In the case of Type-I single panel precoding, the precoding matrix is expressed through the following structure: $\mathbf{W}_k = \mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{W}_{2,k}$,⁴ where \mathbf{W}_1 includes wideband and long-term precoding and $\mathbf{W}_{2,k}$ includes sub-band and short-term precoding [2]. \mathbf{W}_1 is defined by a beam or group of beams pointing in various directions, while $\mathbf{W}_{2,k}$ chooses the group of vectors from \mathbf{W}_1 and applies phase shifts over the polarizations [2].

The beams defined in the wideband precoding matrix \mathbf{W}_1 can be selected based on an index $I_1 \in \mathbf{I}_1$ [19]. This index is composed of subindices $i_{1,1}$ and $i_{1,2}$, which respectively select the horizontal and vertical beam indices m_1 and m_2 [19]. In case the number of configured streams v is higher than 1, I_1 includes a third sub-index $i_{1,3}$ [2]. The $i_{1,3}$ index maps into indices k_1 and k_2 used to offset $i_{1,1}$ and $i_{1,2}$ for the different streams [2]. The offset is calculated based on the horizontal and vertical oversampling factors O_1 and O_2 , and the horizontal and vertical antenna ports N_1 and N_2 of the transmitter (gNB) [2].

Similar to \mathbf{W}_1 , the narrowband precoding matrix $\mathbf{W}_{2,k}$ is addressed by an index $I_2 = i_2$, which maps the phase offsets to be applied for each beam [19]. When using codebook mode 2 instead of codebook mode 1, the I_2 index is divided into $i_{2,0}$, $i_{2,1}$, and $i_{2,2}$ [2]. In this paper we focus on codebook mode 1, and so $I_2 = i_2$.

The indices I_1 and I_2 are used to retrieve the best precoding matrix \mathbf{W}_k from the codebook for each PRB [2]. The indices are obtained using a PMI selection technique, as we will detail in Section 5. The selection is performed at the UE side, and the indices are then submitted to the corresponding gNB in the CSI report. Subsequently, though not mandatory, the gNB uses that \mathbf{W}_k when transmitting in downlink to the UE [2].

The CSI report also includes a RI, which dynamically determines the number of concurrent streams that gNB uses to transmit to its serving UE, i.e., v_u [2]. The RI is estimated based on the interference normalized channel matrix $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_k$ via a RI selection technique, as we will review in Section 4. The Type-I single panel codebook supports $v_u \in 1, 2, \dots, 8$ streams according to [2].

In 3GPP, in order to reduce the amount of data required to report the CSI, the RI is a wideband report, i.e., a single rank is used for all the PRBs, and the PMI has a wideband component (I_1) plus a sub-band component (I_2) that is reported per sub-band instead of per PRB. The number of PRBs per sub-band can be configured according to the number of PRBs in a bandwidth part, as defined in table 5.2.1.4-2 from [2]. For example, for bandwidths including from 73 to 144 PRBs, the permitted sub-band sizes are 8 and 16 PRBs/sub-band.

As of September 2024, the ns-3 open-source 5G-LENA simulator [16] supports Precoding Type I (single-panel) with PMI/RI/CQI reporting (codebook mode 1) including up to 32 transmit antenna ports (N_T) per gNB and up to 4 (R) simultaneous streams per UE, where $v_u \leq R$. As such, in this work, we will exploit such model and extend it to implement and evaluate various and new PMI/RI selection procedures.

4. Rank indicator selection

The rank indicator selection has an important role in MIMO systems, since it indicates the number of streams to be used during transmission. Aggressively selecting higher ranks results in the transmission of more streams with lower power, which can decrease the overall MCS [5], thus reducing the channel capacity. Alternatively, conservatively selecting lower ranks results in the transmission of fewer streams with higher power, which increases the overall MCS [5], at the cost of less concurrent streams, also lowering the channel capacity. There are three major groups of techniques to find the best balance between them: Singular Value Decomposition (SVD)-based with fixed and variable threshold, search-based, and power allocation techniques, like water-filling.

4.1. SVD with fixed threshold

Mathematically, the rank of any matrix $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_k$ can be determined using the singular values extracted from the SVD $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_k^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k = \mathbf{U}_k \mathbf{\Lambda}_k \mathbf{V}_k^H$ [20]. The singular values should be sorted and then analyzed from the highest to the lowest value [21]. A threshold is then used to determine which singular values are significant and which are not. The number of significant singular values is equivalent to the rank [21]. In our system model, the matrix $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_k$ represents the interference normalized channel as observed by its many transmitting-receiving antenna ports in the k th PRB for a pair of gNB-UE devices in the same channel [21]. However, as there are multiple PRBs (K) in the channel, and the RI is wideband, we need a technique to compress/aggregate the values. Different options can be considered. For example, we can average the channel correlation matrices, i.e., $\sum_{k=1}^K \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k$ and then do the SVD to determine a single rank, or we could average the ranks obtained by applying the SVD to the channel correlation of each PRB. Finally, this rank can be reported as the RI in the CSI feedback.

This rank selection with a fixed threshold, however, is not ideal for real MIMO systems that use finite length constellations, due to the side effect of the RI in the MCS, resulting in poor performance [5]. As an alternative, multiple authors have proposed variable thresholds for rank selection, as discussed in the next subsection.

⁴ To simplify the notation, from this section and onwards, we focus on a given gNB-UE pair, and so neglect the subindex u , and just maintain the PRB index k .

4.2. SVD with variable threshold

Variable threshold techniques employ more than one calibrated threshold to minimize incorrect rank selection compared to the results produced by the exhaustive search, which produces the optimal solution given the codebook constraint. Dynamic variable threshold solutions such as those proposed in [5,21–23] allow for calibrations that work across different scenarios for different ranks.

We highlight in particular the dynamic threshold based on the channel capacity increase ratio proposed in [5], which will be referred later as *Sasaoka's* technique. The channel capacity can be calculated as follows:

$$C = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{r=1}^{\min(N_T, N_R)} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_{r,k} p_k}{N_T} \right), \quad (8)$$

where $\lambda_{r,k}$ is the r th highest singular value from \mathbf{A}_k , as extracted by the SVD of the interference normalized channel correlation matrix for the k th PRB, and p_k is the transmit power available for the k th PRB.⁵

The technique proposed in [5] splits the channel capacity in Eq. (8) into increments for each rank, i.e.:

$$\Delta C_r = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_{r,k} p_k}{N_T} \right), \quad (9)$$

so that $C = \sum_{r=1}^{\min(N_T, N_R)} \Delta C_r$. Then, the technique computes the ratio of increase against the baseline case, that is rank 1, and compares it against a threshold function $\alpha(r)$, as shown in Eq. (10).

$$\frac{\Delta C_r}{\Delta C_1} \geq \alpha(r) \quad (10)$$

The threshold function $\alpha(r)$ is a monotonically decreasing linear function (see more details in [5]). The selected rank ($v \leq R$) is then the maximum rank that meets the condition in Eq. (10), i.e., the maximum rank (r) for which the ratio increment is higher than the threshold function for that rank.

4.3. Exhaustive search

The RI $v \leq R$ can be selected by using an exhaustive search of the combination of RI and PMI that maximizes a performance metric, such as the channel capacity. It can be described with the Eq. (11), assuming that D is a function that selects the PMI for a given rank r and interference normalized channel $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_k$ and returns I_1, I_2 and the resulting performance metric for that rank. In Section 5 we see different PMI selection techniques for D .

$$v = \underset{r \in R}{\operatorname{argmax}} D(r, \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k, K) \quad (11)$$

4.4. Power allocation across active streams

Water-filling is a technique that has been widely used in communications over the years, especially in the context of fixed power budget systems [19,24,25] with multiple transmitting antennas N_T . It allocates different power budgets to the different streams, in such a way that the (Shannon) channel capacity is maximized. It then provides an algorithm to determine the power level allocated to each stream and the number of active streams (rank). A simplified version of it can be applied to just determine the number of active streams (i.e., the rank), by using the realistic assumption of equal (and uniform) power allocation across the active streams.⁶ In this case, the rank selection can be determined by computing the capacity with each possible rank, assuming the power is uniformly distributed across the streams inversely proportional to the selected rank (same power to all streams), and then select the rank that gives maximum capacity. So, we compute the channel capacity for increasing number of streams, and not antennas used in the *Sasaoka's* technique. The channel capacity is computed as:

$$C(v') = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{r=1}^{v'} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_{r,k} p_k}{v'} \right), \quad (12)$$

for $v' = 1, \dots, R$, and then the rank is selected as follows:

$$v = \underset{v' \in R}{\operatorname{argmax}} C(v') \quad (13)$$

⁵ Note that our formulation is more general than [5], which does not include interference. This is why in our system formulation the interference plus noise is captured in the interference normalized channel matrix, thus including the spatial dimension, and consequently the channel capacity is affected by the power term and not by the SINR as in [5].

⁶ Note that 3GPP codebooks, Type I and Type II, assume equal power to all streams [2].

Fig. 1. Basic sub-band downsampling techniques.

5. Precoding matrix selection algorithms

Ideally, any given channel has an optimal precoding matrix which can be extracted from the channel matrix information [4]. Using this precoding matrix, however, is challenging, since it would require reporting a large matrix with short durability [2]. To increase the efficiency of the PMI reporting, codebooks such as the one introduced in Section 3 were created. These codebooks have a set of precomputed precoding matrices stored in a matrix addressed by a pair of indices, I_1 and I_2 . Every device has a local copy of said codebook. This allows devices to report only the I_1 and I_2 indices, for their receiver to be able to retrieve a good precoding matrix to be used in a future transmission.

To further reduce the size of the PMI report and better scale with larger bandwidth channels, I_2 indices are reported per sub-band s of the S sub-bands that compose the channel ($s = 1, \dots, S$), and a single I_1 is sent for the entire channel. Sub-bands can contain a different number of PRBs according to the channel bandwidth and configuration, as defined in table 5.2.1.4-2 from [2]. The sub-band values are taken from the PRBs via some form of sub-band downsampling. The downsampling is typically based on averaging, uniform or random sampling of values from PRBs values within a sub-band s . This is represented in Fig. 1, where each column represents the channel gain of a PRB, assuming a single antenna port at the transmitter and receiver. Note, however, that in real communication systems with multiple antenna ports at both the transmitter and receiver, each of the columns would be represented by a channel matrix instead.

From now on, we will work with the compressed channel per sub-band. So, let $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_s$ represent the interference normalized channel at the s th sub-band, $s = 1, \dots, S$. Note that, as PMI is reported per sub-band, then all precoding matrices for each reported sub-band will be applied in the actual transmission of all PRBs in that sub-band. We also define the channel capacity function as $\text{Cap}(\mathbf{W}_s, \bar{\mathbf{H}}_s)$. It calculates the channel capacity of a sub-band s using Eq. (7). The wideband channel capacity can be then computed as the sum of the sub-band capacities, which scales in complexity with $O(N_T N_R S)$, where N_T and N_R are the number of transmitting and receiving antenna ports, and S is the number of sub-bands.

Next, we detail some precoding matrix selection algorithms.

5.1. Ideal precoding matrix

The ideal precoding matrix \mathbf{W}_s for a sub-band s can be extracted directly from the channel matrix of that sub-band for a given rank [4]. Let us decompose the channel correlation matrix $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_s^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_s$ via SVD, i.e., $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_s^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_s = \mathbf{U}_s \mathbf{\Lambda}_s \mathbf{V}_s^H$, then the optimal precoding is $\mathbf{W}_s = \mathbf{V}_s$. We can extract the precoding matrices by repeating this procedure for each sub-band, as shown in Algorithm 1. This procedure is not 3GPP-compliant, as it is not constrained by a codebook-based design and the PMI feedback overhead is prohibitive in a real system. However, it will be used in the evaluations in Section 7 to show the unconstrained upper-bound performance.

5.2. Exhaustive search

The exhaustive search consists on evaluating every single combination of $v \in R$, $I_1 \in \mathcal{I}_1$ and $I_2 \in \mathcal{I}_2$ indices to retrieve precoding matrices. Then searches for the sub-band precoding matrices \mathbf{W}_s that produce the highest wideband Shannon capacity for the given sub-band channels $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_s$. The search is shown in Algorithm 2. The asymptotic complexity of the naive exhaustive search is $O(R|\mathcal{I}_1||\mathcal{I}_2|S)$ iterations of the channel capacity function $\text{Cap}()$. R is the maximum supported rank, limited by the codebook design and the number of antenna ports, i.e., $R \leq N_T$. \mathcal{I}_1 and \mathcal{I}_2 are sets of indices for the precoding matrix, and v is the selected rank. S is the number of Sub-bands (SBs) in a given channel.

Algorithm 1 Ideal Precoding Matrix

```

maxCap ← 0
v ← 1
for all r ∈ {1, ..., R} do                                     ▷ Rank selection
  rCap ← 0
  for all s ∈ {1, ..., S} do
    V ← SVD( $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_s^H \times \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_s$ ).V[:,1:r]}                       ▷ Extract V matrix via SVD, slice up to rank r columns
    sCap ← Cap(V,  $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_s$ )                                       ▷ Compute sub-band capacity with Eq. (7)
    rCap ← rCap + sCap
  if rCap > maxCap then
    maxCap ← rCap
    v ← r
for all s ∈ {1, ..., S} do
  Ws ← SVD( $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_s^H \times \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_s$ ).V[:,1:v]}
return W

```

Algorithm 2 Precoding Matrix Exhaustive Search

```

maxWbCap ← 0
v ← 1
maxWbI1 ← 0
maxI2s[1..S] ← 0
for all r ∈ {1, ..., R} do                                     ▷ RI and I1 selection
  for all I1 ∈ {1, ..., |I1|} do
    wbCap ← 0
    for all s ∈ {1, ..., S} do
      maxSbCap ← 0
      maxI2s ← 0
      for all I2 ∈ {1, ..., |I2|} do
        W ← PrecMatrixCb(r, I1, I2)
        sCap ← Cap(Ws,  $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_s$ )
        if sCap > maxSbCap then
          maxSbCap ← sCap
          maxI2s ← I2
      wbCap ← wbCap + maxSbCap
    if wbCap > maxWbCap then
      maxWbCap ← wbCap
      v ← r
      maxWbI1 ← I1
for all s ∈ {1, ..., S} do                                     ▷ I2s selection
  maxSbCap ← 0
  sMaxI2 ← 0
  for all I2 ∈ {1, ..., |I2|} do
    W ← PrecMatrixCb(v, maxWbI1, I2)
    sCap ← Cap(Ws,  $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_s$ )
    if sCap > maxSbCap then
      maxSbCap ← sCap
      sMaxI2 ← I2
  maxI2s ← sMaxI2
W ← PrecMatrixCb(v, maxWbI1, maxI2s)
return W

```

5.3. Search-free

Search-free typically refers to techniques that completely avoid search procedures. However, when it comes to the selection of PMI, avoiding the search is challenging because the problem does not admit a closed-form solution [12]. Search-free techniques to PMI instead exploit the codebook construction properties to find the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) coefficients l , m and n , which can be translated into the PMI indices $i_{1,1}$, $i_{1,2}$ and i_2 [4,12]. This drastically reduces the search space, eliminating the search for these subindices that comprise the I_1 and I_2 indices transmitted in the PMI report.

In [4], the authors introduce the Linear Phase Estimation (LPE) technique to estimate coefficients l , m and n . These coefficients are calculated based on phases θ_l , θ_m and φ_n , which correspond to the horizontal and vertical inclination of the primary beam [19], plus the phase between the polarized antennas and different panels. The phases are calculated first, via Eqs. (14)–(16), reproduced from [12]. The equations use the number of horizontal and vertical antenna ports of the transmitter (e.g. gNB for the downlink channel), N_1 and N_2 , and the vectors \hat{u}_1 and \hat{u}_1 , which can be constructed in different ways, depending on the technique used. The

\angle operator refers to the angle between the real and complex components of the resulting sum.

$$\hat{\theta}_l = \angle \left(\sum_{k=1}^{N_2} \hat{u}_1^*(k) * \hat{u}_1(N_2 + k) \right) \text{mod } 2\pi \quad (14)$$

$$\hat{\theta}_m = \angle \left(\sum_{k=1}^{N_2-1} \hat{u}_1^*(k) * \hat{u}_1(k+1) \right) \text{mod } 2\pi \quad (15)$$

$$\hat{\phi}_n = \angle \left(\sum_{k=1}^{N_1} \hat{u}_1^*(k) * \hat{u}_1(N_1 N_2 + k) \right) \text{mod } 2\pi \quad (16)$$

The technique to construct \hat{u}_1 and \hat{u}_i in [4] involves the extraction of the right-singular matrix \mathbf{V} of each sub-band channel matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_s$ via SVD. The first ν columns from \mathbf{V} correspond to the ideal precoding matrix for rank ν [26]. Each column is copied to a different vector with different addressing schemes to organize values spatially, as done in tone estimation techniques [4]. These vectors correspond to \hat{u}_1 and \hat{u}_i in Eqs. (14)–(16).

After the phases have been estimated, the DFT coefficients can be calculated with Eq. (17), reproduced from [12]. The product of the phases, along with the number of horizontal and vertical antenna ports, N_1 and N_2 , and the oversampling factors in the horizontal and vertical directions, O_1 and O_2 , results in an estimate of the coefficients.

$$\hat{\mathbf{i}} = \left\lfloor \frac{O_1 N_1}{2\pi} \hat{\theta}_l \right\rfloor, \hat{\mathbf{m}} = \left\lfloor \frac{O_2 N_2}{2\pi} \hat{\theta}_m \right\rfloor, \hat{\mathbf{n}} = \left\lfloor \frac{2}{\pi} \hat{\phi}_n \right\rfloor \quad (17)$$

The DFT coefficients are then mapped to the $i_{1,1}$, $i_{1,2}$ and i_2 indices via the tables with prefix 5.2.2.2.1 in [2]. To find the precoding matrix in the codebook, it is still required to determine the rank and then the $i_{1,3}$ index for ranks $\nu \in [2, 3, 4]$, which is typically done via exhaustive search over the possible ranks. After the LPE estimation, the search for the missing $i_{1,3}$ and the rank ν that produces the highest channel capacity is executed. This search scales with $O(R)$.

The same LPE technique is used in [12], however, the procedure for finding phases θ_m , θ_l and ϕ_n is replaced by a less convoluted approach. Vectors \hat{u}_1 and \hat{u}_i are the first columns of the orthogonal factor matrices U_2 and U_3 [12]. These matrices are extracted by Higher-Order Singular Value Decomposition (HOSVD) of the channel tensor \mathcal{H} , considering the channel matrix for every sub-band, given by $\mathcal{H} = S \times_1 U_1 \times_2 U_2 \times_3 U_3$ [27]. The HOSVD can be easily computed with the help of the Tensor Toolbox for MATLAB or Python [28]. We refer to this selection technique as *Maleki's* technique.

5.4. Optimized searches

There are a few alternatives with optimized searches, including the algorithm proposed in [5], which splits the selection of the rank from the selection of the precoding matrix, reducing the search space for the latter. The rank selection is based on the capacity increment each rank can provide against the baseline rank 1 [5], detailed in Section 4.2.

The PMI is then selected via on the maximization of the mutual information [5], which is done via an exhaustive search for every sub-band and precoding matrix for the selected rank and all $I_1 \in \mathcal{I}_1$ and $I_2 \in \mathcal{I}_2$ combinations. This direct estimation for the rank reduces the exhaustive search cost by up to $R - 1$ times. This does not take into account the rank estimation cost.

6. Proposed techniques

We propose two techniques: one for fast rank selection based on power allocation, and a pruning strategy for the exhaustive PMI search space.

6.1. Power allocation based rank selection

The proposed rank selection technique is performed via a variation of the water-filling, which typically adjusts the allocated power to each band in such a way that more power is allocated to the most unfavorable bands, following Eq. (12) [5,25]. In our case, however, water-filling is applied to streams, where 3GPP imposes a practical constraint of having the same power across streams.

The proposed method is shown in Algorithm 3. To reduce the number of SVDs computed to extract the singular values, we average the different bands. Since rank is reported as a wideband property, this approximation is sensible. The technique also takes into account two other parameters, R and CF. The R parameter is the upper threshold for rank selection, and it is required to accommodate different codebooks available to report the RI, I_1 , and I_2 values. R is ultimately limited by the minimum number of antenna ports at the transmitter and the receiver. The CF calibration factor is used to adjust the fast rank selection. It can be estimated via exploratory simulation campaign of a specific scenario. The appropriate value for each scenario can be determined using a gradient descent technique with the goal of minimizing the mean selected rank difference when compared to the exhaustive counterpart.

In the implementation, the computation of C_{avg} is made in the caller of the rank selection method, and passed in the place of $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$, preventing its recomputation. The calibration is performed using the exhaustive PMI search to collect the optimal precoding matrix-bound rank for a given antenna array, power, and position configuration.

Algorithm 3 Proposed Power Allocation (PA) based rank selection

```

 $C \leftarrow \bar{\mathbf{H}}^H \times \bar{\mathbf{H}}$ 
 $C_{avg} \leftarrow \sum_{sb=0}^S C_{sb}$ 
 $\Lambda \leftarrow \Lambda(C_{avg})$ 
 $v \leftarrow 1$ 
 $vCap \leftarrow 0$ 
for all  $r \in \{1, \dots, R\}$  do
   $cap \leftarrow 0$ 
  for all  $stream \in \{1, \dots, r\}$  do
     $cap \leftarrow cap + \log_2(1 + abs(\Lambda_{stream})/r/CF)$ 
  if  $cap > vCap$  then
     $vCap \leftarrow cap$ 
     $v \leftarrow r$ 
return  $v$ 

```

▷ Average all sub-bands
 ▷ Singular values in decreasing order
 ▷ Rank limited by the codebook
 ▷ Capacity estimate corrected by CF

Ideally, predetermining the rank would reduce the total RI/PMI complexity by up to $R - 1$ times when compared with the exhaustive search, that has to select the best PMI among all ranks. Computing the rank with the proposed algorithm scales with $O(S(N_T N_R)^2 + (S N_T N_R) + (N_T N_R)^3 + \frac{R^2}{2})$ complex floating point operations. This complexity can be decomposed in the complexities of the Hermitian transpose and matrix multiplication to obtain their correlation $O(S(N_T N_R)^2)$, the averaging of sub-bands $O(S N_T N_R)$, the SVD decomposition for the extraction of the singular values $O(N_T N_R)^3$ and finally the search for the highest capacity $O(\frac{R^2}{2})$.

6.2. Fast PMI search

We have derived a new fast PMI search, which basically, as compared to the exhaustive search, splits the CSI feedback search into the wideband components (RI and I1) and sub-band components (I2) into three separate simplified steps. This results in a significant reduction of the search space.

The first step is selecting a rank with our Algorithm 3, or a comparable alternative such as Sasaoka's variable threshold described in Section 4.2. The second step is performing the search for the I_1 indices using the wideband C_{avg} , also used by the rank selection. The third and final step is performing the search for the I_2 indices for each sub-band. The three steps are shown in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Precoding Matrix Fast Search

```

 $C \leftarrow \bar{\mathbf{H}}^H \times \bar{\mathbf{H}}$ 
 $C_{avg} \leftarrow \sum_{sb=0}^S C_{sb}$ 
 $v \leftarrow RankSelection(C_{avg}, R, CF)$ 
 $maxCap \leftarrow 0$ 
 $maxWbI1 \leftarrow 0$ 
 $maxI2s_{1..K} \leftarrow 0$ 
for all  $I_1 \in \{1, \dots, I_1\}$  do
  for all  $I_2 \in \{1, \dots, I_2\}$  do
     $\mathbf{W} \leftarrow PrecMatrixCb(v, I_1, I_2)$ 
     $wbCap \leftarrow Cap(\mathbf{W}_1, C_{avg})$ 
    if  $wbCap > maxCap$  then
       $maxCap \leftarrow wbCap$ 
       $maxWbI1 \leftarrow I_1$ 
for all  $s \in \{1, \dots, S\}$  do
   $maxCap \leftarrow 0$ 
  for all  $I_2 \in \{1, \dots, I_2\}$  do
     $\mathbf{W} \leftarrow PrecMatrixCb(v, maxWbI1, I_2)$ 
     $sCap \leftarrow Cap(\mathbf{W}_s, C_s)$ 
    if  $sCap > maxCap$  then
       $maxCap \leftarrow sCap$ 
       $maxI2s_s \leftarrow I_2$ 
 $\mathbf{W} \leftarrow PrecMatrixCb(v, maxWbI1, maxI2s)$ 
return  $\mathbf{W}$ 

```

▷ Step1
 ▷ Step2: I_1 selection
 ▷ Step3: I_2 s selection

This allows us to reduce the search space for the $I_1 \in I_1$ and $I_2 \in I_2$ selection from $O(R|I_1||I_2|S)$ to $O(|I_1||I_2| + |I_2|S)$ combinations when comparing the exhaustive search to the proposed fast search. S is the number of sub-bands. R is the maximum

Table 1
Supported simulation parameters range.

Simulation Parameter	3GPP 5G NR's Value range	Simulator Value range	Source
Carrier frequency	[0.5–100] GHz	[0.5–100] GHz	[18,33]
Channel Bandwidth	FR1: [5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100] MHz, FR2: [50, 100, 200, 400, 800, 1600, 2000] MHz	[6–65536] PRBs (PRB bandwidth depends on numerology)	[18,31,33]
Subband size	[1, 4, 8, 16, 32]	[1 - numPRBs]	[2], this work
Antenna Elements	[1–∞]	[1 - uint64_t]	[18,30,33,34]
Polarizations	[1, 2]	[1, 2]	[18,30,33,34]
Numerology	[0–6]	[0–6]	[16,32]
Antenna Ports	[1–32]	[1–32]	[2,29]
Rank	[1–8]	[1–4]	[2,29]
Precoding	Codebook-based Type-I (SU-MIMO) and Type-II (MU-MIMO)	Codebook and non-codebook-based Type I (SU-MIMO)	[2,29], this work

supported rank. $|I_1| = N_T N_R |I_{1,3}|$. N_T is the number of transmitting ports. N_R is the number of receiving ports. $|I_{1,3}| = 4$ if the rank $v \geq 2$ and $|I_2| = 4$.

Assuming a gNB with $N_T = 16$ ports and a UE with $N_R = 4$ ports. Rank $R = 4$, which requires $i_{1,3} = 4$. Numerically, the exhaustive has to explore 73 728 parameter combinations, while the proposed search has to explore 1096.

7. Evaluation and analysis

In this section, we present the simulation scenario and the simulation results of various RI and PMI selection methods and sub-band downsampling techniques. For the performance assessment, we used the 5G-LENA NR module for ns-3 network simulator [17]. 5G-LENA is an open-source end-to-end full-protocol-stack network simulator to simulate 5G NR technology, with 3GPP-compliant PHY and MAC layers [16], and which got updated in [29] to include hybrid beamforming and closed-loop MIMO mechanism, following precoding Type I [2].

Table 1 presents a comparative overview of key simulation parameters supported by 3GPP specifications for 5G NR and the 5G-LENA simulator implementation. The first column lists the simulation parameters. The second column lists the range of values for each parameter according to 3GPP technical reports and specifications [2,18,30–32]. The last column lists the range of values for each parameter configurable by the 5G-LENA simulator [16,29] and the 3GPP spatial channel model implementation from ns-3 [33,34]. As shown, the simulator aligns closely with the parameter ranges defined in 3GPP technical specifications for 5G NR, while allowing for non-standardized settings of interest. Regarding channel bandwidth, while 3GPP specifies discrete bandwidth values depending on the frequency range, the simulator adopts a more flexible model allowing for arbitrary bandwidth. While 3GPP 5G NR provides specific values for subband sizes, 5G-LENA generalizes this with completely flexible sub-band sizes. Antenna elements are configurable within broad limits, where the simulator's upper bounds are constrained only by system data types. The number of antenna ports are constrained by the MIMO codebook implementation. While 3GPP 5G NR allows MIMO ranks up to 8, the current simulator implementation is limited to rank 4, which does not require transmitting two Transport Blocks (TBs) simultaneously. Additionally, the simulator currently implements only Type-I precoding for single-user MIMO (SU-MIMO), and lacks support for Type-II codebook-based precoding used in multi-user MIMO (MU-MIMO) configurations, as specified in [2].

To carry out the present analysis, we have implemented in the simulator the various PMI/RI selection techniques that we have reviewed through this paper.

7.1. Scenario

The simulation scenario involves two UEs attached to two separate gNBs interfering with each other. One of the UEs is static, while the other UE moves away from its primary gNB in the direction to the secondary gNB, as shown in Fig. 2.

The simulation parameters are listed in Table 2. A remote server was configured to send enough traffic to saturate the wireless link. A precoding Type I Single Panel implementation supporting up to rank 4 and 32 antenna ports was used for all the simulations. The 3GPP spatial channel model described in [18] and implemented in ns-3 in [33,34] is used. Ideal channel and interference estimation is assumed, upon received CSI-RS.

The simulation campaigns were executed in an Ampere Mt.Collins server with 160 CPU cores at 1–3 GHz.

For the key performance indicators, we focus on the achieved user throughput and the execution time to assess the performance versus complexity trade-off. The user throughput is measured as the correctly received bytes over the simulation time measured at the IP layer, in Mbps. The execution time is measured as the time needed to complete the simulation, in s. In addition, we also illustrate the mean rank and mean MCS selected for various gNB-UE distances, for a proper understanding of the behavior of the PMI/RI selection techniques.

Fig. 2. Simulated topology.

Table 2
Simulation parameters.

	Parameter	Value
Channel	Model	3GPP (TR 38.901) UMa
	Frequency	3.5 GHz
	Bandwidth	20 MHz (106 PRBs)
gNBx2	Numerology	0
	Bearer 5QI	80
	Tx Power	41 dBm
	N_1	8
	N_2	2
	O_1	4
	O_2	4
	Polarizations	2
Antenna ports	32	
UEx2	Tx Power	23 dBm
	N_1	8
	N_2	2
	O_1	4
	O_2	4
	Polarizations	2
	Antenna ports	32
	Simulation	Total simulated time
MCS Table		MCS Table2 (256 QAM) [2]
AMC model		Error-model based
Target BLER		10%
HARQ retransmissions		Enabled, up to 4
HARQ method		Incremental Redundancy
HARQ processes		20
Channel estimation source		CSI-RS
Traffic	Type	UDP
	Packet size	1000 bytes
	Packet period	10 μ s
	Total traffic	822.4 Mbps

7.2. Simulation results

The simulation results for the RI selection techniques, PMI selection techniques and side effects of sub-band downsampling are listed next. All plotted values are means between 20 separate runs using different seeds for each listed combination of RI/PMI techniques. Rank and MCS values are the average mean value of the reported Rank and MCS reported throughout the simulation via the CSI feedback.

The t -test [35] $T(z_i) = k_i, p_i = s_i$ was used to determine whether the difference in results for the techniques were statistically significant. T is the t -test applied to two populations that are being compared. The populations of size $z_i = 20$ in this case are the 20 simulation runs for each combination of RI/PMI techniques and distances. The result of the test is the t -test statistic k_i and significance $p_i = s_i$. We use $p_i < 0.05$ as the threshold to reject the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis in all cases is that both populations at a given distance are statistically the same according to a metric, such as throughput and simulation time. The null hypothesis indicates that the results found here, favoring one technique or another, were selected by chance. The p -values of each of the 23 different tested distances between the gNB1 and UE1 are then combined using Fisher's method $F(z_F) = k_F, p_F = s_F$. The population size for Fisher's is $z_F = 23$, while k_F is the Fisher's statistic and $p_F < 0.05$ indicates we can reject the null hypothesis for all distances [36]. In other words, we can statistically conclude the two techniques are different.

Fig. 3. Results for different RI techniques with interference (2 gNBs and 2 UEs).

7.2.1. Rank selection

We compare four RI selection techniques. The first is the SVD-based solution with fixed threshold (detailed in Section 4.1). The second is Sasaoka’s SVD-based solution with variable threshold, described in Section 4.2. The third is the exhaustive search, detailed in 4.3. The fourth is our proposed solution using power allocation, detailed in Section 6.1. We compare them with the case of not using MIMO feedback, for which fixed rank 1 and no digital precoding gain is considered.

The different rank selections and related results are shown in Fig. 3. From the SVD (green downwards triangle) rank results in Fig. 3b, the behavior of the fixed threshold is demonstrated. Unless the threshold is calibrated for each link of each scenario, it will pick either a higher or lower rank rather than approaching the rank picked by the exhaustive search (blue dots). Since it is infeasible to do this, a better alternative is necessary.

The two alternatives implemented are Sasaoka’s channel capacity increment ratio (magenta leftwards triangles) and our proposed Power Allocation-based technique (named PA, in cyan upwards triangles). Note that in this particular scenario, the UE throughput was not significantly impacted by the different RI selection techniques, shown in Fig. 3a. This happened because the rank was compensated by a change in the MCS, see Fig. 3c, which is not always the case.

In terms of execution time, SVD with fixed threshold, SVD with variable threshold (Sasaoka) and PA RI are all bound by the time spent to extract the singular values via SVD, which is shown in Fig. 3d.

Empirically, we found that our PA RI selection technique does not provide a generic solution, requiring calibration in different scenarios. This can be confirmed by looking at the results in Fig. 4b. The results show how the same technique performed in a scenario without the interference of a second UE/gNB pair. The PA rank selection diverged very strongly from the exhaustive search after the first kilometer. Like in the previous case, there was no significant impact on the UE throughput for this particular scenario.

Sasaoka’s RI selection based on the channel capacity increment, on the other hand, behaved the same for both cases, with and without interference. Not requiring specific calibration for every scenario makes this technique the preferable among those implemented, and it was chosen to be used along with different PMI selection techniques in the next section.

7.2.2. PMI selection

The results for the PMI selection are presented in Fig. 5. The sub-figure rows represent the different performance metrics: throughput, rank, MCS and execution time of the simulation. The columns represent different sub-band downsampling techniques, with 1, 8 and 16 PRBs per sub-band. The sub-band downsampling used takes a random PRB inside the SB as the SB value to perform the RI/PMI selection.

Fig. 4. Results for different RI techniques without interference (1 gNB and 1 UE).

The results for the ideal precoding matrix (Ideal) are shown in cyan upwards triangles, and are included as an upper bound performance reference without the constraints of the codebook. The exhaustive search (Full) is shown in green downwards triangles. The proposed PMI search (Fast) is shown as blue circles. The pruned search technique proposed by Sasaoka [5] and the search-free technique proposed by Maleki [12] are shown as yellow and magenta triangles pointing right and left, respectively.

Fig. 5.a shows the case where no sub-band downsampling is performed. That is, a single PRB for each sub-band. All the techniques performed better than with no MIMO feedback (red stars). The results show that Ideal precoding matrix selection achieves 1.26x higher UE throughput than the Full PMI selection. This indicates that the Type-I single panel codebook significantly limits the potential throughput increase MIMO could provide, ignoring the much higher feedback overhead.

The performance in terms of UE throughput of Sasaoka, Maleki and our proposed Fast technique are graphically very similar to the reference Full technique. This similarity, however, is just graphical, as shown in Table 3. For Sasaoka, there was a statistically significant ($F(23) = 67.255, p = 0.035$) mean reduction of 2.1% when compared to the Full technique. For Maleki, there was a reduction of 8.1% ($F(23) = 382.143, p = 0.000$). For the proposed Fast technique, there was a reduction of 3% ($F(23) = 83.111, p = 0.001$). There was no significant difference between Sasaoka and Fast in terms of UE throughput ($F(23) = 32.708, p = 0.955$). The reduction in throughput results from the rank and MCS selection, as shown in Fig. 5b and c. The loss in performance, however, can be justified by a large reduction in algorithmic complexity and respective execution time, which indeed happened for Maleki's and our proposed Fast technique.

The speedup of the techniques proposed in the literature and in this paper were compared to the Full exhaustive RI/PMI search. The speedup values were 0.785x, 3.536x, and 3.721x for the Sasaoka, Maleki, and Fast techniques, respectively. The small speedup difference between Maleki and Fast is statistically insignificant ($F(23) = 174.101, p = 0.000$). These results are shown in Table 3. The PMI selection proposed by [5] (Sasaoka, yellow) performs very poorly. This is somewhat expected from an exhaustive search using the mutual information of the channel as the optimization metric. The mutual information is calculated using expensive matrix determinant calculations, done for each sub-band for each combination of I_1 and I_2 . The PMI selection proposed by [12] (Maleki, purple leftwards triangles) has similar runtime performance than our Fast selection (blue dots), however offers a lower overall throughput, Fig. 5a, due to a more aggressive rank selection, Fig. 5b. Its main advantage is not requiring any form of calibration, which is a very important characteristic of the solution.

The results with sub-band downsampling of 8 PRBs and 16 PRBs for each sub-band are shown in second and third columns of Fig. 5. Applying the sub-band downsampling by changing the configurable size of the sub-band as specified in 3GPP in table 5.2.1.4-2

Fig. 5. RI/PMI selection results without and with sub-band downsampling.

from [2], produces very similar results with the scenario with no downsampling, except for the execution time. The last row of Fig. 5 shows the execution time of all the techniques are drastically reduced by the sub-band downsampling. As a result, the speedups of Maleki and Fast in respect to Full are reduced to 1.123x and 1.157x for 8 PRBs/SB, or 1.086x and 1.105x for 16 PRBs/SB, as shown in Table 3.

7.2.3. Bandwidth side effects

Additional simulations were executed to verify that the RI/PMI selection behaves consistently across different bandwidths, in spite of the sub-band averaging of the channel covariance matrix, as proposed in the Fast PMI selection. The gNB and UE transmission powers were adjusted to keep the transmit power spectral density stable across simulations. The bandwidths, transmission powers and sub-band sizes used in both cases are listed in Table 4.

The results of the simulations without sub-band downsampling are presented in Fig. 6. The first row shows the spectral efficiency across different channel bandwidths (columns). The spectral efficiency remains consistent across most bandwidths, except for the 80 MHz case (Fig. 6q). In this particular case, saturation is not achieved due to the application generating only 800 Mbps of traffic. No statistically significant variation is observed across the various bandwidths in terms of spectral efficiency, average rank, or average MCS with the proposed Fast PMI selection. This invariance holds despite the use of per-PRB averaging of the channel covariance matrix. Regarding execution time per unit of bandwidth (bottom row), the Ideal, Maleki, and Fast PMI selection methods exhibit

Table 3

Mean speedup μ and standard deviation σ between different techniques and the Exhaustive/Full RI/PMI selection. The Ideal technique is listed to demonstrate the maximum achievable throughput without the codebook constraints.

Technique	$\frac{PRBs}{SB}$	UE throughput speedup ($\mu[\sigma]$)	Total simulation speedup ($\mu[\sigma]$)
Exhaustive RI + Ideal PMI	1	1.272 [0.347]	1.674 [0.382]
	8	1.260 [0.334]	0.985 [0.139]
	16	1.264 [0.338]	1.037 [0.163]
Sasaoka RI + Sasaoka PMI	1	0.979 [0.077]	0.785 [0.219]
	8	0.978 [0.075]	1.033 [0.157]
	16	0.979 [0.077]	1.078 [0.170]
Exhaustive RI + Maleki PMI	1	0.919 [0.126]	3.536 [0.956]
	8	0.917 [0.123]	1.136 [0.176]
	16	0.919 [0.126]	1.100 [0.182]
Sasaoka RI + Fast PMI	1	0.970 [0.083]	3.721 [0.938]
	8	0.967 [0.083]	1.170 [0.177]
	16	0.969 [0.086]	1.119 [0.187]

Table 4

Alternative parameters for studying bandwidth-related effects.

Bandwidth (MHz)	gNB Tx Power (dBm)	UE Tx Power (dBm)	Sub-band sizes (PRBs)
5	32	17	[1,4]
10	35	20	[1,4]
20	38	23	[1,8]
40	41	26	[1,16]
80	44	29	[1,32]

Table 5

Mean speedup μ and standard deviation σ between different techniques in respect to Exhaustive/Full RI/PMI selection using different downsampling techniques for 16 PRBs/SB.

Technique	Downsampling technique	UE throughput speedup ($\mu[\sigma]$)
Exhaustive RI + Ideal PMI	First PRB	1.268 [0.342]
	Random PRB	1.264 [0.338]
	Average PRB	1.257 [0.330]
Sasaoka RI + Sasaoka PMI	First PRB	0.981 [0.078]
	Random PRB	0.979 [0.077]
	Average PRB	0.966 [0.087]
Exhaustive RI + Maleki PMI	First PRB	0.919 [0.126]
	Random PRB	0.919 [0.125]
	Average PRB	0.932 [0.123]
Sasaoka RI + Fast PMI	First PRB	0.971 [0.087]
	Random PRB	0.969 [0.086]
	Average PRB	0.963 [0.085]

linear scalability with bandwidth. In contrast, the Sasaoka and Full PMI selection methods become more expensive with additional bandwidth.

Similar trends are observed in the simulations employing sub-band downsampling, which follow the 3GPP-defined maximum sub-band sizes for the respective bandwidths, as shown in Fig. 7. A reduction in execution time per Hertz can be observed in the bottom row, primarily due to the decrease in the number of sub-bands S as a result of downsampling, which limits the search space of PMI selection and reduces the complexity of matrix operations. However, the improvement observed between the 5 MHz and 10 MHz cases (Fig. 7d and h, respectively), despite maintaining a constant sub-band size of 4 PRBs, suggests that a substantial portion of the simulation time is independent of the bandwidth for small bandwidths. This fixed computational overhead becomes diluted as the bandwidth increases, as can be observed in Fig. 7l, p, and t.

7.2.4. Sub-band downsampling side effects

We ran a campaign to evaluate the impact of different sub-band downsampling techniques on the overall RI/PMI selection. The sub-band downsampling was fixed to 16 PRBs per SB. The results are shown in Fig. 8. Visually, there is no significant difference, other than the rank selection deviation of Sasaoka's and our Full techniques, Fig. 8f versus Fig. 8j, which are both using Sasaoka's RI selection and were equally impacted.

Fig. 6. RI/PMI selection results for different channel bandwidths with sub-bands of 1 PRB.

Statistically, however, the difference in the observed UE throughput caused by the downsampling techniques was insignificant ($p > 0.05$) for the Ideal, Full, and Maleki techniques. Sasaoka and our Fast technique have statistically different results for the different combinations of FirstPRB, AveragePRB and RandomPRB for some tested distances, but on average are equivalent. The UE throughput speedup for the different downsampling techniques applied to each of the RI/PMI techniques is shown in Table 5. F-values and p-values are omitted due to redundancy.

8. Conclusions

This work proposed two techniques, one Power-Allocation (PA) based technique to select the RI, and the Fast technique to select the PMI. The proposed RI selection technique calibration is sensitive to interference, requiring a more complex calibration model to match the behavior of the exhaustive search. Sasaoka’s RI selection based on channel capacity increment ratio produced similar results to the exhaustive RI, independently of changes in the scenario. The proposed PMI selection technique was very effective in speeding up the simulation, especially when no sub-band downsampling was used. Even with sub-band downsampling, the speedup is still significantly higher than the one provided by other state-of-the-art techniques, at a very low UE throughput loss. Other techniques resulted into lower total simulation speedup, with either similar losses to user throughput in the case of Sasaoka’s PMI, or much bigger losses in user throughput in the case of Maleki’s PMI.

Fig. 7. RI/PMI selection results for different channel bandwidths with maximum sub-band downsampling for each bandwidth, according to 3GPP.

As the number of antenna ports increase, solutions to decrease the computational cost of RI/PMI become more important. These techniques help devices conserve power when generating the CSI feedback. They also reduce the time to run more large and complex simulations, which do not have the luxury of offloading these computations to specialized hardware.

Multiple techniques for RI and PMI described in the literature were implemented and integrated into the 5G-LENA NR module for the ns-3 network simulator. Sub-band downsampling was also implemented in the simulator. All code is publicly available in the 5G-LENA source-code repository,⁷ allowing other researchers to easily implement and evaluate the end-to-end performance of their RI and PMI techniques in the future, instead of relying on custom simulators.

⁷ <https://gitlab.com/cttc-lena/nr/-/releases/v4.0>.

Fig. 8. RI/PMI selection results with different sub-band downsampling techniques for sub-bands of 16 PRBs each.

Acknowledgments

This work has received funding from Grant PID2021-126431OB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and “ERDF A way of making Europe”, TSI-063000-2021-56/57 6G-BLUR project by the Spanish Government, and Generalitat de Catalunya grant 2021 SGR 00770.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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